

INTERNAL MARKETING MODEL FOR BANKING SECTOR

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ABSTRACT

Due to growing private sector, globalization, liberalization, demanding customers, changing technologies there is radical change in the banking sector. It is one of the service organizations that are functioning to improve service quality. To improve the service quality motivation and satisfaction of internal customers are very important. Internal marketing is such a concept that improves the exchange between organization and internal customers that leads to better performance of the organization. Nowadays internal marketing is not only to improve service quality but the overall development of the organization. To implement internal marketing successfully there is need to make clear about its path. There is not one process to implement it. Its process can vary according to the type of the industry, size of the organization, function of the organization etc. To utilize and implement this concept fruitfully it is necessary to devised new models of it.

In this research paper, a new model of internal marketing for the banking industry is developed. Elements that are used in this model are internal marketing activities, motivation and satisfaction of employees, Inter-functional coordination, external customer satisfaction and increasing profitability. This model is very beneficial for the banking sector to implement internal marketing.

KEYWORDS

Internal marketing, Banking sector, internal market, internal marketing model

1. INTRODUCTION

Internal marketing is a growing concept. After the journey of 35 years this concept has been developed and changed according to the situations and the goals of the organization. This notion is significant for every type of organization. It is useful for service sector as well as manufacturing industry. But the problem is in its

implementation process. Various researches has been conducted that revealed that it is very beneficial conception for retaining internal customers, to improve the performance of the organization, profitability of the organization, motivation of internal customers, creating internal customer orientation in the organization etc. It makes positive impact on sustainable development of the organization, for gaining competitive advantage, to satisfy and retain customers, organizational development and growth etc. The basic essence of this notion is that internal customers or employees should be served in such a way that makes positive impact on organizational performance i.e. financial as well as non-financial that leads to sustainable development of the organization.

Banking industry is facing challenges such as rapidly changing market, new technologies, economic uncertainties, competition, and demanding customers. There is fierce competition in financial sector. Banking sector is one of service organization that is facing the same. Thus, it is necessary to improve service quality of the banking sector. Banks play vital role in economic development of every nation. Due to privatization, globalization, liberalization there is drastic change in this sector. Various studies proved that internal marketing plays vital role for improving banking performance and development. Internal marketing is unambiguous concept because it is found similar with various other concepts like human resource practice, strategy to improve service quality, source of competitive advantage, marketing practice etc. Thus to give exact meaning of internal marketing it is necessary to devised process of its implementation. There is not a one rule of thumb to implement internal marketing. There is need to develop various models on internal marketing process so that organization and stakeholders can be benefited. Thus in this paper to implement internal marketing successfully in the banking industry a new model is develop

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Internal marketing

According to Copper and Cronin (2000), internal marketing is a tool to provide better service to customer.¹ Various researchers focused on 'service encounter' which means the time in which consumer interacts with the employee for service. According to C. Bhattacharjee customer interacts with company, product, people, facilitates or communications represent 'moment of truth' because it influence customer's judgment and image about the firm. Thus, internal customers play an important role in organization. To improve the service quality motivation

¹ Cronin J. John; Cooper Jack (2000) "Internal Marketing: A Competitive Strategy for the Long-Term Care Industry, Journal of Business Research 48, 177-181

and satisfaction of internal customers are very important. Therefore there is need to create marketing environment inside the organization for the internal customers.

According to Berry (1981) as in the traditional marketing there is exchange between organization and external customer. In internal marketing, there is exchange between internal customers. In external marketing customer buy goods and services and in internal marketing internal customers buy jobs. Organization is a market and employees are treated as customers in the internal marketing concept². In the organization, we have to employ strategy of shaping job products according to need of employees. Thus, it is necessary to provide jobs that satisfy and motivate them.

2.2 Internal market

Internal market is the first market of the organization, where internal customers need to inform, educate, about organizational mission, policy and benefits of its product and its services and also customer requirement or expectations. Before selling product and services in the external market it is necessary that employees understand it. Employees need knowledge about organizational mission, policy and customer expectation so that they can work effectively. In the internal marketing context Organization need to sell their mission strategies, policies to employees first. Berry s logic of organization selling job products. Job products does not means task to perform. It includes each and every thing that employees can used to perform their work. Job products include: There are two levels of Job products two levels

- Strategic level: Organizational mission, policies, strategies
- Tactical level: task to perform, work environment to perform, Different things required to perform that job. (it includes material and human elements)
- Material elements means: techniques required to perform the job
- Human elements means – people required to contact for performing any activity.)

There are several studies of internal marketing on banking industry for example,

² Berry L.L. (1981). "The employee as customer", Journal of retail Banking, 3 (1), pp. 33-39

It is found that internal marketing concept is very useful for the improvement of the banking industry. More studies are required in this field to give better insight in this concept and develop more models to implement it successfully.

2.3 Internal marketing and internal market

According to Ahmed and Rafiq (2002) job product is not limited to task that performed by employees. It also includes training needs, levels of responsibility, career opportunities, working environment, and involvement in decision making. Internal products are created by managers to engage employees in the organizations corporate responsibility and sustainability philosophy. Good internal products results to engage employees in corporate responsibility to invest time and effort in it. ³

Internal marketing is to improve relationship between employees and also make them customer oriented at all levels depicted by Gummesson et al (1991). This means, employees making relationship to make them customer oriented. Banking industry makes impact on the economy of the country. In the TQM concept also importance of both customers is to improve customer service. Due to increasing competition banking sector compete to provide better service to their customers. In the internal market there is an employee who makes relationship with each other because they are using human element to perform job. Employees cannot perform job alone there is need to interact with other employee. Organization is selling job products then employees start to utilize its resources to perform that job. Marketing is not get end after selling the product. Now the marketing is also focusing how the customers are using their product. Are they satisfied by using it? Relationship develops in the internal market. Employees communicate with each other formally and also informally. How they perform is also depend on the relationship between employees. There is supply chain. If the job product is not satisfactory there is need to make change in them and also convince the internal customer. Internal customers play vital role to improve the organizational system and makes positive impact on the customers.

³ Hernandez-Sanchenz et al, (2012) "Internal marketing for engaging employees on the corporate responsibility journey", vol 8 (2), pp.275-307.

2.4 MODELS OF INTERNAL MARKETING

In the internal marketing literature there are three most important model of it which are:-⁴

Berry model:- According to this model 'employees are treated as customers and jobs as product'. Berry focused on marketing like activities internally. This model measure result by perceived service quality, competitive advantage, and customer satisfaction.

Groonroos model:-

After the drawbacks of Berry model Groonroos developed a new model. In this model Groonroos focused on interactive marketing. This model gives outcomes of perceived service quality, customer satisfaction and increased profitability.

Meta-model: Due to shortcomings of Berry and Groonroos model Pervaiz Ahmed introduced a new model called as Meta-model. Special feature of this model is it elaborated relationship between customer satisfaction & customer loyalty. By this employee word of mouth promotion is also increased. In this model formula for employee satisfaction are:-

$$Es=f(T, D, P)$$

Es=Employee satisfaction F=function

T=training

D=discretion

P=participative management

This model cleared that Employee satisfaction depends on training, employee discretion, & Participative management.

⁴ Rafiq M. & Ahmed, P.K. (2002) "Internal marketing tools and concept for customer.

2.5 Studies on internal marketing and banking industry

Banking industry is one of the centre of attention for the internal marketing research. Various authors revealed that internal marketing plays imperative role for the organizational success. Mishra (2010) service organization understands the importance of employees this led to the use of internal marketing practices in the organization.

Many scholars researched on effect of internal marketing in employee retention and they found that there is positive effect on it. Many researchers also worked to see impact of internal marketing on employee job satisfaction and this proved that internal marketing results in employee satisfaction. Main intention here is that to make employees feel that management considers the employees and their needs.

Lings and Greenly (2005) recommended providing better service and customer satisfaction it is necessary to encourage and motivate employees through the internal marketing. It improves the service quality of organization. This means that to improve service quality of organization, motivation of employee plays an important role. Internal marketing is the practice through which employees can be motivated.⁵

It is necessary to know what gives satisfaction and motivation to employees to implement internal marketing successfully. Many private companies are giving opportunities to their employees. However, as we see today's internal market of organization is full of boredom, stress, conflict, and tiredness etc. employee satisfaction gives way to remove these problems of internal market. It is necessary to understand internal market before jump to external market. It is difficult to face external market without concern of internal market. It is the internal market that makes positive impact on customers, and organizational success.

Six dimensions for internal marketing used by A Vijaya kameshwari et al which are work content, training, work environment, superior support, coworker, recognition. They studied job satisfaction of employees in State Bank of India. Confirmatory factor analysis used along with SEM Structural equation modeling to find out relationship. SPSS and AMOS 20 used for statistical analysis. It is also observed by A Vijaya kameswari et al that internal marketing is suitable for all types of organization. In one of the study of Saudi Arabia on banking employees

⁵ Lings; I.N. and Greenly, G.E. (2005). "Measuring internal market orientation," Journal of service Research, vol 7, No3 pp 290-306

reveals that internal marketing impacts perceptions of organizational commitment to employees (PBCMT) and rewards, employee empowerment.⁶

Che Ha, Abu Bakar & Jaffar (2007) studied internal marketing as marketing tools to attract and retain the best employee to improve organizational performance. They suggested 12 constructs of internal marketing are:-

. Inter-functional coordination and integration

Customer orientation

Marketing like approach

Job satisfaction

Empowerment

Employee motivation

Quality of service

Employee development

Vision of the organization

Strategic rewards

Internal communications

Senior leadership

An empirical study conducted by Myriam on a sample of 116 banking customer advisors and 3 clients of each (348 client). They found that customer orientation has a mediating effect between internal marketing and service quality perception. Thus, customer orientation plays important role to improve the service quality.

Shekary et al. (2012) studied on sample of 233 bank managers in Mashhad City, Iran. They found that internal marketing is affective means for organizational commitment. They used structural equation modeling to test the hypothesis of relation between observed and latent variables. Kyriazopoulos et.al. (2007) researched on 'implementing internal marketing through employee's motivation'. They surveyed in 356 bank branches of Greece and studied internal marketing influences on work commitment of employees. They also proposed how internal marketing linked with market orientation concept. They found that public sector banks are not following the

⁶ Al A Faisal (2015)"An investigation of internal marketing and its effects on employees in the banking sector in Saudi Arabia., vol20, issue3, pp.176-190.

performance appraisal and motivational program but they are committed to the organization due to job security.

Private sector banks employees are motivated but their commitment was found low.⁷

Ahmad Naveed identified positive effect of internal communication, training and motivation on employee retention in Pakistan. According to Quester and Kelley (1999) for the implementation of internal marketing there is need of combination of people such as marketing manager, Account manager, managing director, and human resource manager. Ibrahim Ahmed et al. researched on commercial banks in Egypt. They found internal marketing has significant effect on banks performance.⁸

Thus we see that internal marketing concept is very useful for job satisfaction of banks, commitment of bank employees, employee retention, and bank performance. More studies are required in this field. For the successful implementation process of internal marketing it is precondition to develop models of it. Thus in this research paper one research model is proposed for the banking sector.

3.1 RESEARCH PROPOSED MODEL

Fig 1.1 represents internal marketing model for banking industry. This model is developed on the basis of internal marketing concept contributed by Berry, Pervaiz Ahmed and Groonroos. In the model first and foremost element of internal marketing activities are applications of marketing like activities. After application of marketing like techniques i.e internal marketing research, segmentation, communication, internal pricing, product policy and promotion. For the implementation of marketing application of marketing like techniques is the first step. Thus it is also applicable to the internal marketing model.

Fig 1.1 model clarifies that first important step in the internal marketing is the application of marketing like activities inside the organization. Before internal customers motivation it is necessary to understand them very well. With the help of Internal marketing activities employees need and desires can be understand by the organization. After understanding need of employees organization is ready to sell job product. For this it is necessary to motivate employees to purchase job product. When employee's needs are satisfied then they are

⁷ Kyriazopoulos et.al. (2007), "Implementing Internal Marketing through Employees Motivation" POMS 18th Annual Conference May 04-07

⁸ Ghoneim Ibrahim Ahmed et al.,(2014)"Effect of internal marketing Adoption on the performance of the commercial banks in Egypt"
Proceedings of 9th international Business and social science Research conference Dubai, UAE.

motivated with the training, discretion, and participative management. . These are the three most important elements that motivate employees.

Fig. 1.1 Banking model of internal marketing

Staff and front line employees make impact on external customer satisfaction. Front line employees are directly do interaction with the external customers. Staff makes indirect impact on the external customers. In the organization there is interaction between the employees. All of the employees are important for the internal marketing process. Inter-functional coordination improved with these activities and makes impact on external customer service and organizational performance. After all these process external customers s are satisfied with the service and it gives profit to the banks by retaining and attracting external customers. External customer plays an important role to the bank's profitability by generating revenue to the banks. It leads to the profitability of the banking by generating revenue, sustainable development, improving organizational culture etc.

3.2 ELEMENTS OF MODEL

❖ Application of marketing like techniques internally

According to various researchers internal marketing is marketing inside the organization. In the internal market organization is a market and employees are customers. Various authors i.e. Piercy and Morgan, Reardon and Enis, Gilmore and Carson etc. described internal marketing activities. According to Ozretic Dosen internal marketing

activities are internal market research, segmentation, communication, internal pricing, product policy, and sales and distribution.

- Segmentation-Segmentation is a process of dividing market according to needs and desire of customers. Market segmentation can be demographic, psychographic, and behavioral. In the internal market firms develop some central benefits in the mind of the employees or internal customers. Organization offering various benefits to the employees without knowing their choices then it is wasting time of it. Jobber (2005) gave three internal market segments, sympathizers, neutral, and opponents. Sympathizers are who support changes, neutral are who have no opinion in respect to organizational change, and opponents are who are against changes.

Segmentation process can be varying according to need of organization and employee mutual benefits.

- Communication- In the current scene lack of communication is the major problem. To improve communication top management involvement is very necessary. Flow of reliable information builds trust between employees. In the banking sector there is need to encourage informal communication for best practice of internal marketing activities.
- Internal Pricing –Internal marketing is an investment thus every investment has its price. Before investing cost and benefit analysis is required.
- Product policy-To sell product in the market it is prerequisite to prepare product policy. Product policies are programmes and services through which management do actions on employees.
- Sales and distribution- Distribution means how product reaches to the target customer. In the internal market also to reach job product to the internal customers there is need of proper distribution channel. It should be such that it saves time, energy etc. of employee.
- Promotion- in the internal market promotion is required to promote internal activities of the organization. Promoting by giving incentives, bonus, public relation etc. It helps to attract, retain and motivate employees.

Promotional activities can be used such as internal sale, advertising, internal website, internal incentive and disincentive.⁹

- ❖ **Motivated and satisfying employees:** Pervaiz explained in his meta-model of internal marketing that to satisfy employee's three elements are most important i.e. training, discretion and participative management.

Various researches also proved that these elements works best to motivate and satisfy employees.

- Training
- Discretion
- Participative management

❖ **Inter-functional coordination Inter-functional coordination**¹⁰

Inter-functional coordination is the extent of cooperation between the departments and different functions inside the organization. In the process of internal marketing all the activities are need to be coordinated to implement internal market orientation which leads to successful market orientation.

- **Providing service to customers** -Employees are motivated and they provide excellent service to their customers by improving their inter-functional coordination.
- ❖ **External customer satisfaction**-By implementing internal marketing employees become customer conscious and customer oriented. By this external customers are satisfied. Internal customers are very important for the organization thus, it is important to attract, train, motivate retain customer conscious employees.¹¹

- ❖ **Increasing profitability:** Internal marketing plays an important role in financial and non-financial performance of the organization. By retaining and attracting customers it increases its market share and leads to profitability. By implementing internal marketing organization is able to gain competitive advantage, sustainable development, increases employee loyalty and improving overall organizational performance.

⁹ Strunje Zeljko; Paliaga Marko, (2011), "Research of Implementation of Internal Marketing in Companies in the Republic of Croatia", Vol. 24, No.1 (107-121).

¹⁰ Kanovska Lucie (2012), "Interfunctional coordination at Hi-tech Firms," vol 23, No.1, ISSN No. 1392-2785.

¹¹ Op.cit.

Internal marketing is the way to gain competitive advantage in respect to people management. It improves the service quality of the organization by providing excellent service. Internal marketing process improves interaction between people of the internal market and makes a positive impact on external market.

• CONCLUSION

Internal marketing is a broad concept. This research paper focused on internal marketing model of banking industry. Various researches have been proved that it is very beneficial concept. There is need to develop models on this concept. The model developed in this research gives better insight about the concept to the banking sector. For the right implementation of internal marketing there is need to develop model of internal marketing that would be beneficial for the banking sector.

Elements of the model in that is developed in this research are application of marketing techniques internally (segmentation, communication, Internal pricing, product policy, sales and distribution, promotion), Motivated and satisfying internal customers (training, discretion, participative management), Inter-functional coordination, external customer satisfaction and increasing profitability. In today's competitive and dynamic environment it is necessary to gain competitive advantage to survive and prosper. Human resource or intangible assets plays an important role to get success. Internal marketing improves service quality of the organization. By focusing on external as well as internal customers equally organization develops the culture to gain sustainable competitive advantage. Internal marketing plays an eminent role in business performance. Employee loyalty is linked with customer loyalty and profitability. Therefore improving employee loyalty is necessary for customer loyalty and organizational profitability.

Limitation of the study

In this study new model is developed that is not empirically tested. Internal marketing model only for banking sector was developed.

Future scope of the study

The research proposed model developed in this research can be empirically tested in banking sector as well as other sectors for the further study. After empirically tested this model can be generalized.

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